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Rheological design and characterization of Al₂O₃-based pastes for the direct ink writing of CFD-optimized woodpile scaffolds

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ABSTRACT

This study presents a strategy for the design and fabrication framework of Direct Ink Writing (DIW) manufactured Al₂O₃-based scaffolds, integrating computational fluid dynamics (CFD) and experimental rheological optimization. First, CFD simulations were performed under gas flow conditions to evaluate the impact of internal geometry on the permeability, pressure drop, unit mass flow and outward mass flow rate, comparing Woodpile (WP) architectures with 90° and 45° strut orientations. The WP90 configuration promotes high mass flow, evidenced by a lower pressure drop. While the WP45 configuration created a more intricate fluid pathway, maximizing gas-scaffold interactions at the cost of higher flow resistance. Once the 3D structure was studied, the rheological behaviour of the multicomponent paste comprising PVP, hydroxypropyl cellulose, Darvan, and graphite for DIW was experimentally optimized to achieve the high-viscosity and shear-thinning properties required for the WP structures printability. The effects of solid loading (44-48 vol% vs. 57-61 vol%) and particle morphology in aqueous Al₂O₃-YSZ and Al₂O₃-Sepiolite pastes were investigated. Crucially, the study elucidates a system-dependent interaction mechanism where the graphite pore former acts as a reinforcing agent in granular Al₂O₃-YSZ pastes but functions as a lubricant in fibrous Al₂O₃-Sepiolite networks. This sequential approach ensures that the scaffold's performance is optimized at the design stage while maintaining high structural fidelity during the extrusion process.

1. Introduction

Although ceramic scaffolds have been predominantly explored for tissue engineering [1,2], electronics [3], energy storage [4], and wastewater treatments [5] they also hold promise in gas separation applications due to their tunable porosity, high surface area, and versatility in material choice [6]. Three-dimensional printed ceramic scaffolds are gaining attention due to their structural advantages and potential to act as monolithic supports in catalytic and gas separation processes.

The Direct Ink Writing (DIW) has emerged as a prominent technique for fabricating advanced ceramic structures, offering an optimal balance between cost-effectiveness and production efficiency [7]. This process involves the micro-extrusion of a ceramic paste through small nozzles, typically ranging from 50 to 2000 μm in diameter, to create strut-based structures in three-dimensional space following the displacement of nozzle through computer guided pathway [8].

A successful paste for DIW processing requires balancing two competing demands: a sufficiently high ceramic load to maintain homogeneity and minimize shrinkage after sintering, achieving specific rheological properties for smooth extrusion while retaining structural integrity and shape fidelity of the strut after deposition [9,10].

This requires the careful selection of additives that play a crucial role in stabilizing ceramic particles and modifying paste performance. Pastes suitable for DIW usually are concentrated suspensions of ceramic particles (typically 40-50 vol% or 60-80 wt% [10,11]), in a liquid carrier medium (usually water [11]).

In addition, particle morphology and size distribution of ceramic powders are critical in designing high solids-loading pastes. Spherical particles enhance flow by minimizing internal friction, while the agglomeration of irregular particles and their abrasive nature promote clogging and deterioration of the nozzle in the conformation equipment.

Among technical ceramics, aluminum oxide (Al₂O₃) is a preeminent choice. It is widely valued for its excellent physical properties, including

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a high melting point, hardness, strength, chemical stability and wear resistance [7]. Furthermore, its abundance and cost-effectiveness have established it as one of the most versatile technical ceramics for widespread industrial use. Of particular relevance to this work, Al_2O_3 is one of the most used material in heterogeneous catalysis, where it is extensively employed as a catalyst support due to its tunable surface acidity/basicity and thermal/mechanical stability [12]. This combination of robust physical properties, economic viability and proven catalytic utility makes Al_2O_3 an ideal material for the advanced catalyst scaffolds investigated in this study.

For high quality prints, there should be at least a small proportion of organic additives (<2 vol % or ≤ 1 wt% [9,13]) that help tune the interparticle forces and manipulation of printed geometries after drying. Commonly used polyelectrolytes with amine or carboxylic groups include polyacrylate (PAA), polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) and polyethyleneimine (PEI) [14]. Moreover, the incorporation of dispersants or plasticizing agents, such as cellulose-based polymers, can improve the extrudability of the pastes for DIW [15].

The incorporation of these functional components, alongside the high concentration of primary ceramic powders needed to minimize the shrinkage of the structure during drying and sintering steps, makes the overall formulation of a printable DIW paste a significant challenge. Usually, the as-printed ceramic structures are subjected to drying in ambient or humidified environments to prevent crack formation and warping due to drying [16].

Once dried, the parts are debinded to remove organic components and then sintered. These steps may lead to significant shrinkage, which can vary depending on the solid loading, organic content and the sintering process on its own. Therefore, these dimensional changes should be considered during the initial design phase when high dimensional fidelity structures are required [9,10].

The successful extrusion and deposition of such a complex multi-component, high-solid-loading suspension for DIW is governed entirely by its rheology (SI file Section 1). Among these rheological properties, shear-thinning behavior, where viscosity decreases at higher shear rates, and structure recovery after the shear forces are removed are the most critical two during the DIW processing. Shear-thinning is essential for enabling the multicomponent paste to flow easily through the printing nozzle under pressure while rapidly recovering its viscosity to ensure optimal filament formation and shape retention after the extruding and sintering.

While DIW affords precise control over macroscopic porosity (pores >100 μm) through manipulation of filament (strut) deposition design parameters, the regulation of sub-50 μm porosity, particularly at scales below individual filament dimensions, remains challenging [8]. This limitation is significant, as both meso-porosity and microporosity are critical for high-performance catalysis applications. To address this, carbon-derived materials like graphite particles can be used as a sacrificial pore former to achieve controlled microporosity. When incorporated into the ceramic paste and subsequently removed through heat treatment (oxidization and volatilization), these particles create a network of interconnected micropores within the final sintered structure [17].

The DIW processing route leads to the fabrication of strut-based geometries, among which the woodpile (WP) architecture is one of the most widely implemented for catalytic applications. It consists of multiple layers that are arranged in a crisscross fashion [18]. Filaments within each layer are aligned in one direction, while those in the subsequent layer are deposited at a specific angle (typically 90°) relative to the preceding one.

The crisscross nature of the structure creates open spaces (macropores) within the printed scaffold, facilitating mass flow throughout the interconnected channels, providing at the same time improved mechanical properties of the overall structure [19]. The size and distribution of these macrostructural porosity features can be controlled by adjusting the filament spacing and layer height, which are typically

related to filament diameter. These scaffolds result in highly interconnected and ordered macrostructural porosity structures, making them highly suitable for applications requiring improved mass flow and separation efficiency [20].

In this work we present a strategy for the integration of Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulation within the design of ceramic scaffolds with optimized strut-based WP geometries for gas fluids (CO_2 and H_2). The optimization of the WP geometry was conducted in COMSOL Multiphysics 6.3, evaluating key parameters, such as macrostructural porosity, pressure drop, mass flow and an outlet velocity within the gas domain through CFD analysis. Once the optimal scaffold geometry was determined, the requirements for DIW ceramic paste to produce it were clear. That is, the successful fabrication of computationally-derived geometries is critically dependent on the formulation and resulting rheological properties of the DIW printing paste.

The rheological survey is structured around two key objectives (1) to experimentally formulate and compare two distinct aqueous paste systems (Al_2O_3 -YSZ and Al_2O_3 -Sepiolite) in combination on the effect of graphite pore former on rheological parameters; and (2) to establish quantitative printability criteria by directly comparing the measured rheological properties of each paste with their observed fabrication outcomes.

By integrating these CFD insights and experimental rheology optimization approaches, this work provides a practical framework for designing and manufacturing high-performance catalytic scaffolds through DIW technique, ensuring that simulation-optimized heterogeneous catalyst structures are manufactured to high fidelity to the intended design through formulated and printable ceramic materials.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Materials

The primary ceramic powders utilized in this study were alpha aluminum oxide (α - Al_2O_3) with a median particle size (d_{v50}) of 5–7 μm (Thermo Scientific Chemicals Inc., Dreieich, Germany) and yttria-stabilized zirconia (YSZ). The YSZ powder, composed of zirconium (IV) oxide (ZrO_2) stabilized with 3 mol% yttrium (III) oxide (Y_2O_3) and exhibiting a d_{v50} of ≈ 200 nm, was sourced from Tosoh Europe B.V. (Amsterdam, Netherlands). Sepiolite ($\text{Mg}_4\text{Si}_6\text{O}_{15}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) was supplied by SAMCA (Sociedad Anónima Minera Catalano-Aragonesa, Zaragoza, Spain). The as-received sepiolite was subjected to an acid treatment for impurity removal, yielding a silica-based fibrous powder with a specific surface area (SSA) of $330 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ and zeolitic channels of 0.37×1.06 nm.

Several organic additives were employed to formulate the pastes. DARVAN C-N (Vanderbilt Worldwide Ltd., London, UK) was used as a surfactant for the ceramic powders. Graphite UF2, with a d_{v50} of ≈ 4 –5.5 μm (Graphit Kropfmühl/AMG Mining AG, Hauenberg, Germany), was incorporated as a sacrificial pore-forming agent. Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) K15 (average molecular weight, $M_w \approx 10,000$ g/mol) and K30 ($M_w \approx 58,000$ g/mol) were obtained from Thermo Scientific Chemicals Inc. (Dreieich, Germany). PVP K15 functioned as both a surfactant for the graphite and a short-chain binder, whereas PVP K30 served as the principal binder. Additionally, hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (METHOCEL™ K3 Premium LV, DuPont, Geneva, Switzerland) was utilized as a binder. Distilled water was used as the solvent for all formulations.

2.2. Paste preparation methodology

Aqueous ceramic pastes were formulated using two distinct solid phase systems. The first system, based on Al_2O_3 -YSZ, was prepared with total solid loadings ranging from 44 to 48 vol%, maintaining a constant Al_2O_3 : YSZ volumetric ratio of 60:40. The second system, based on

Al_2O_3 -Sepiolite, was formulated with solid loadings between 57 and 61 vol% at a constant Al_2O_3 : Sepiolite volumetric ratio of 95:5.

The general preparation procedure is schematically illustrated in Fig. 1. Initially, the primary ceramic powders (Al_2O_3 and 3YSZ) were dispersed in aqueous solution containing Darvan C-N to create a stable colloidal suspension. This suspension was subsequently ball-milled for 4 h using $\varnothing = 10$ mm zirconia media in High-Density Polypropylene (HDPP) jars. Following the separation of the milling media from the suspension, the remaining components, including sepiolite (for the Al_2O_3 -Sepiolite formulations), organic binders and the pore-forming agent (where applicable) were incorporated. Each component was added individually and homogenized for 1 min at 2000 rpm using a planetary centrifugal mixer (ARE-250, Thinky Corp., Tokyo, Japan). To complete the homogenization process, additional 7 mixing cycles of 1 min length were applied. The final pastes were stored at 4 °C for a period of 2 to 7 days before their use.

2.3. Simulation details

As a starting point for the CFD simulation, the Reynolds number (Re) was calculated to determine the flow regime within the WP scaffolds. The Re represents the dimensionless ratio of inertial to viscous forces and is defined by equation (1):

$$\text{Re} = \frac{\rho u L}{\mu} \quad (\text{Equation 1})$$

where ρ is the fluids density, μ the fluids dynamic viscosity, u the flow speed, and L is the characteristic length defined as the strut diameter (700 μm). Using the parameters at normal conditions, the employed values for CO_2 and H_2 gases were $\rho_{\text{CO}_2} = 1.830 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$, $\mu_{\text{CO}_2} = 14.830 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ Pa s}$, $\rho_{\text{H}_2} = 0.090 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$, $\mu_{\text{H}_2} = 8.920 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ Pa s}$ [21] respectively, with an inlet velocity (V_i) of $1 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ m s}^{-1}$.

Calculated Re values were $\text{Re}_{\text{CO}_2} \approx 8.64 \cdot 10^{-3}$ and $\text{Re}_{\text{H}_2} \approx 7.06 \cdot 10^{-4}$. Although the classical transition criterion for smooth internal pipe flow

Fig. 1. Process flowchart illustrating the multi-stage paste preparation process. The key stages include: (1) dispersing the ceramic powders to form a stable colloidal suspension; (2) ball-milling the suspension for 4 h to ensure agglomerant elimination and homogenization; (3) separating the suspension from the milling media; (4) sequentially incorporating additives, which include sepiolite for the Al_2O_3 -Sepiolite system, organic binders, and the pore-forming agent (where applicable), via planetary mixing; and (5) storing the prepared paste at 4 °C.

occurs at $Re \approx 2,300$, the stacked struts in this WP configuration can promote earlier transitions because of internal geometries. However, since the obtained Re values are several orders of magnitude below unity ($Re \ll 1$), the flow operates in the creeping flow (Stokes flow) regime. Consequently, a laminar flow model was strictly appropriate and selected for the CFD module in COMSOL® 6.3. The simulation employed a Representative Elementary Volume (REV) with the bottom face as the inlet ($V_i, P = 0$) and the top face as the outlet for the flow at atmospheric pressure (1 atm), and no-slip boundary conditions for the scaffold walls.

The cylinder in the WP configuration were represented for 700 μm in diameter, while the spacing 400 μm was selected and a 30% of splicing was considered among the simulated four layers. These arrangements were labeled as WP90 and WP45, depending on the angle among the layers.

Numerical calculation of parameters such as porosity, pressure drop, mass flow and outlet velocity in the gas domain were obtained using the CFD simulation module implemented for the developed gas (H_2 and CO_2) flow behavior through the integration of the boundary conditions at the REV interfaces at each WP configurations.

The porosity (ϕ) of the gas domain can be calculated using the REV and the total volume (V_T) for WP90 and WP 45 in Equation (2) [22]:

$$\phi = \frac{REV}{V_T} \quad (\text{Equation 2})$$

Parameters related to the gas flow behaviour were obtained from the simulation of laminar flow from CO_2 and H_2 streams. Permeability, pressure drop, unit mass flow and outward mass flow rate were determined from the developed flow behaviour across the REV. Following the Darcy law, the permeability (κ), pressure drop (ΔP) and mass flow rate (m) were calculated as follows [23]:

$$\kappa = \frac{\mu u_{out}}{\Delta P} \quad (\text{Equation 3})$$

$$\Delta P = \frac{-(P_2 - P_1)}{REV L} \quad (\text{Equation 4})$$

$$m = \frac{\text{unit mass flow}}{REV \text{ width}} \quad (\text{Equation 5})$$

where, μ is the fluids dynamic viscosity u_{out} is the outlet velocity, P_1 and P_2 are the inlet and outlet pressure respectively. REV L and REV width are the REV length and cross section area.

2.4. Direct ink writing

The woodpile scaffolds were fabricated using a custom-built DIW system based on the robocasting technique. The DIW system is equipped with a pressure-controlled reservoir to supply the formulated ceramic paste to the deposition head. An auger-based mechanism within deposition head regulated the paste extrusion. A conical nozzle with an internal diameter of 700 μm was employed for the layer-by-layer deposition of the paste. The extrusion process was performed at room temperature under ambient humidity conditions. To generate the computationally designed WP90 and WP45 woodpile architectures, the strut pattern was rotated by 90° and 45°, respectively, for each subsequent layer, following the geometries established by the computer-aided design (CAD) models. Cohesion between successive layers was achieved by programming a 10% interpenetration of the nozzle tip, maintaining a strut spacing of 400 μm , consistent with the parameters established in the CFD model. Scaffolds composed of 12 to 14 layers were printed to obtain the final green state structures for subsequent post-processing thermal treatments. Following deposition, the green bodies underwent freeze-drying to ensure uniform moisture removal, thereby preventing warping and preserving dimensional stability during this critical post-printing phase. This controlled drying protocol effectively mitigates moisture-induced stresses that could jeopardize the structural integrity

of the components prior to sintering, which was carried out at 1500 °C with a 4-h dwell time to achieve final consolidation.

2.5. Rheological characterization

Rheological characterization was performed using a rotational rheometer (Haake Mars II, Thermo Scientific, Germany) equipped with a 20 mm diameter parallel plate geometry. For all measurements, the gap was set to 1 mm, and a solvent trap was utilized to prevent sample dehydration during testing. The rheological properties of the pastes were evaluated through a series of rotational and oscillatory tests. The oscillatory measurements, which included stress amplitude sweeps and time-dependent recovery tests, were conducted at a constant frequency of 1.6 Hz. This value was established *a priori*, as preliminary experiments confirmed that all paste formulations exhibited a stable LVR at this frequency. Results were analyzed according to the procedures described in Supporting File (Section 3. Implemented Protocol for Rheology Analysis).

3. Results

3.1. Numerical simulation outcomes

The fluid domain for the gas flow simulations was established by performing a Boolean difference operation between the solid strut patterns and a Representative Elementary Volume (REV), defined as a $5 \times 5 \times 2.5$ mm block. The two woodpile geometries were defined by the angle between struts in successive layers: 90° for the WP90 configuration and 45° for the WP45 configuration. This process isolates the void space available for gas transport within the scaffold architecture. The resulting reconstructed three-dimensional fluid domains for both the WP90 and WP45 configurations are represented in Fig. 2.

Within the constructed domain, tetrahedral meshing was applied for the volume, constricted and adjusted for fluid flow dynamics. For WP 90, the mesh volume is $2.28 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ m}^3$ and the surface area $2.02 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ m}^2$ (Fig. 2e). While for WP 45, slight modifications were observed for the mesh volume (Fig. 2f), decreasing to $2.20 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ m}^3$ and the surface area decreased to $1.99 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ m}^2$.

The geometrical and fluid flow evaluation from the CFD simulation of the porosity, permeability, outlet velocity, surface area and the related REV values for WP90 and WP45 gas domains are presented in Table 1.

The CFD simulation using inlet of CO_2 and H_2 streams with $1.00 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m s}^{-1}$ velocity was developed. The representative surface from pressure and velocity streamline distributions are presented in Fig. 3 (a-c) for WP90 and (b,d) for WP45 using CO_2 stream since the distribution using H_2 stream is similar to the represented in Fig. 3.

While the qualitative flow patterns were similar for both gases, the quantitative outputs showed clear differences attributable to their distinct physical properties. The calculated values for pressure drop, unit mass flow and outward mass flow for both the CO_2 and H_2 streams are summarized in Table 2. This data highlights the influence of gas properties (i.e., dynamic viscosity and density) on the resulting fluid dynamics within the scaffolds.

3.2. Rheological characterization and printability of ceramic pastes

The rheological properties of the two aqueous paste systems, Al_2O_3 -YSZ and Al_2O_3 -Sepiolite, were systematically investigated to establish a robust formulation for DIW conformation process of simulated woodpile structures. The analysis focused on the influence of two key parameters: total solid loading and the concentration of a graphite-based pore forming agent. The viscoelastic response and structural recovery of each paste were directly correlated with their structure retaining performance within section 3.3.

Fig. 2. Gas fluid flow domain reconstruction. From the difference between the Representative Elementary Volume (REV) of a $6.25 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ m}^3$ block and the cylindrical extrudes of $700 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter, arranged in WoodPile (WP) crisscross fashion with 90° (WP90) (a) and 45° (WP45) (b) among 4 layers. The obtained REV from WP90 (c) and WP45 (d) represent the domain for the gas flow simulation. Tetrahedral meshing optimized for fluid flow was applied on WP90 (e) and WP45 (f) respectively.

Table 1

Comparison of the calculated parameters from CFD simulation results using $1.00 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m/s}$ stream as inlet in the gas domain from WP90 and WP45 scaffolds configuration.

Configuration	Porosity (%)	Permeability (m^2)	Outlet velocity (m/s)	Surface area (m^2)	Fluid domain volume (m^3)
WP90	36.53	1.88×10^{-9}	3.79×10^{-5}	2.02×10^{-4}	2.28×10^{-8}
WP45	35.34	1.35×10^{-9}	3.70×10^{-5}	1.99×10^{-4}	2.20×10^{-8}

3.2.1. Influence of solid loading on printability of Al_2O_3 -YSZ pastes

The effect of solid loading on the viscoelastic properties of the Al_2O_3 -YSZ pastes was evaluated using oscillatory stress amplitude sweeps on formulations containing 44, 46 and 48 vol% solids, (each containing 20 vol% of pore former). The results, presented in Fig. 4, show that all formulations exhibited the desired viscoelastic behavior, with the storage modulus (G') consistently higher than the loss modulus (G'') at low shear stresses, indicating a predominantly solid-like, “gelled network” structure. To quantify these observations, key rheological parameters including yield stress (τ_y), flow stress (τ_f) and equilibrium storage modulus (G_{eq}) were extracted from the curves and are summarized in Table 3.

As the solid loading was increased from 44 to 48 vol%, the paste stiffness increased significantly. As quantified in Table 3, the equilibrium storage modulus (G_{eq}) increased by two orders of magnitude from $1 \cdot 10^3 \text{ Pa}$ to $4 \cdot 10^5 \text{ Pa}$. While the 44 and 46 vol% pastes exhibited a clear yield point and a subsequent transition to liquid-like behavior ($G'' > G'$). Whereas, the 48 vol% formulation maintained an extremely high stiffness and did not show a crossover point within the tested stress range, as indicated by the non-determinable (N.D.) flow stress. This excessive rigidity required extrusion pressures exceeding 6 bar during printing trials, rendering the 48 vol% paste unsuitable for the DIW process.

Based on these findings, the structural recovery behavior was assessed only for the printable 44 and 46 vol% pastes (Fig. 5). These time-dependent tests simulate the extrusion-deposition sequence, where

the paste experiences high shear in the nozzle followed by a period of rest. The 44 vol% paste exhibited slow and incomplete structural recovery, with G' failing to significantly surpass G'' even after 150 s. This behavior predicted poor shape fidelity. In contrast, the 46 vol% paste demonstrated relatively rapid and efficient recovery; G' quickly surpassed G'' and approached its initial value, indicating the fast recovery of the particle network required to support the as printed strut structure.

3.2.2. Influence of pore former content on printability of Al_2O_3 -YSZ pastes

Following the identification of 46 vol% as the optimal solid loading, the influence of the pore former concentration was investigated by comparing pastes containing 15 and 20 vol% graphite. The stress amplitude sweeps for these formulations are shown in Fig. 6. The results, summarized in Table 4, indicate that increasing the pore former content from 15 to 20 vol% led to a stiffer paste, with the equilibrium storage modulus (G_{eq}) doubling from $1 \cdot 10^4 \text{ Pa}$ to $2 \cdot 10^4 \text{ Pa}$. The yield stress (τ_y) and flow stress (τ_f) also increased significantly, from 18 Pa to 33 Pa and from 152 Pa to 420 Pa, respectively.

3.2.3. Influence of solid loading on printability of Al_2O_3 -Sepiolite pastes

For the Al_2O_3 -Sepiolite system, the effect of solid loading on rheology was investigated using pastes with 57, 59, and 61 vol% solids (each containing 20 vol% pore former). As shown in the stress amplitude sweeps (Fig. 7), increasing the solid loading resulted in a significant increase in paste stiffness.

The quantitative data, estimated from these curves, is presented in Table 5. The 57 vol% paste exhibited a weak viscoelastic network, with a low storage modulus and yield stress. The 61 vol% paste, in contrast, was excessively stiff, which is reflected in its high G_{eq} and τ_y values, requiring high extrusion pressures (>6 bar) that led to its exclusion from further testing. The 59 vol% formulation demonstrated a robust solid-like response with a well-defined yield point, identifying it as the most promising candidate.

The structural recovery tests (Fig. 8) reinforced these findings. The 57 vol% paste recovered its structure very slowly and incompletely. In contrast, the 59 vol% paste exhibited rapid and near-complete structural recovery, with G' quickly re-establishing higher values over G'' , identifying a rapid return to a stable, solid-like state.

Fig. 3. Gas flow simulation of WP90 and WP45 woodpile configurations using $1.00\text{-}10\text{-}4\text{ m s}^{-1}$ CO_2 stream. 3D surface of pressure distribution for WP90 (a) and WP45 (b). Streamline distribution for velocity domain WP90 (c) and WP45 (d). 2D slicing of the velocity magnitude developed within WP90 (e) and WP45 (f) scaffold.

Table 2

Comparison of the parameters from the developed fluid flow simulation of CO_2 and H_2 $1.00 \times 10\text{-}4\text{ m s}^{-1}$ streams on the WP90 and WP45 scaffolds configurations.

Configuration	Pressure drop ($\text{N}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)	Unit mass flow ($\text{kg}\cdot(\text{m}^2\text{s})^{-1}$)	Outward mass flow rate ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$)
WP90 CO_2	0.29	$6.94\cdot 10^{-8}$	$1.73\cdot 10^{-12}$
WP45 CO_2	0.40	$6.77\cdot 10^{-8}$	$1.69\cdot 10^{-12}$
WP90 H_2	0.18	$3.41\cdot 10^{-6}$	$8.53\cdot 10^{-11}$
WP45 H_2	0.24	$3.33\cdot 10^{-6}$	$8.32\cdot 10^{-11}$

Table 3

Summary of measured values of yield stress (τ_y), yield flow stress (τ_f) and equilibrium storage modulus (G'_{eq}) for 44, 46 and 48 vol% pastes calculated within linear viscoelastic region (LVR) in Fig. 4.

Paste	τ_y (Pa)	τ_f (Pa)	G'_{eq} (Pa)
44 vol%	4.17	22.3	$1\cdot 10^3$
46 vol%	34.2	423	$2\cdot 10^4$
48 vol%	144	N.D.	$4\cdot 10^5$

Fig. 4. Viscoelastic properties of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-YSZ}$ pastes as a function of solid loading. The storage (G') and loss (G'') moduli are plotted against applied shear stress for pastes with 44, 46, and 48 vol% solids, each containing 20 vol% pore former. Increasing solid content leads to a significant increase in stiffness (G'_{eq}).

3.2.4. Influence of pore former on printability of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Sepiolite}$ pastes

Finally, the effect of the pore former on the optimized 59 vol% $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-}$

Fig. 5. Structural recovery tests for $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-YSZ}$ pastes with 44 and 46 vol% solid loading (20 vol% pore former). The plot shows the evolution of G' and G'' over time after a 30 s period of high shear. The 46 vol% paste demonstrates significantly faster and more complete overall recovery.

Sepiolite paste was examined by comparing formulations with 20 vol% and 30 vol% graphite (Fig. 9).

In this system, increasing the pore former content to 30 vol% had the opposite effect to that observed in the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-YSZ}$ system. The addition of pore former drastically weakened the viscoelastic network, causing a

Fig. 6. Influence of pore former content on the viscoelastic properties of 46 vol % Al_2O_3 -YSZ pastes. The plots compare the stress sweep results for pastes containing 15 and 20 vol% graphite, showing an increase in stiffness with higher pore former content.

Table 4

Summary of measured values of yield stress (τ_y), yield flow stress (τ_f) and equilibrium storage modulus (G'_{eq}) for 15 and 20 vol% pore former content, calculated within LVR.

Paste	τ_y (Pa)	τ_f (Pa)	G'_{eq} (Pa)
15 vol%	18	152	$1 \cdot 10^4$
20 vol%	33	420	$2 \cdot 10^4$

Fig. 7. Viscoelastic properties of Al_2O_3 -Sepiolite pastes as a function of solid loading. The storage (G') and loss (G'') moduli are plotted against shear stress for pastes with 57, 59, and 61 vol% solids (20 vol% pore former). The 59 vol% paste shows a desirable balance of stiffness and a clear yield point.

significant reduction in both G' and G'' . This suggests that in the presence of fibrous sepiolite particles, excess graphite acts as a lubricant, disrupting the Al_2O_3 -Sepiolite particle network and reducing interparticle friction. Quantitatively, as shown in Table 6, this weakening was reflected in a reduction of all key parameters. This modification of the rheological properties resulted in enhanced flowability, lowering the

Table 5

Summary of measured values of yield stress (τ_y), flow stress (τ_f), and equilibrium storage modulus (G'_{eq}) for 57, 59, and 61 vol% Al_2O_3 -Sepiolite pastes (20 vol% pore former), calculated from the data in Fig. 7.

Paste	τ_y (Pa)	τ_f (Pa)	G'_{eq} (Pa)
57 vol%	$3 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.02	0.3
59 vol%	0.1	0.7	7.0
61 vol%	0.2	3.8	104

Fig. 8. Correlation between structural recovery and printability for Al_2O_3 -Sepiolite pastes. (a) Recovery test results for 57 and 59 vol% pastes, showing immediate recovery of the 59 vol% formulation.

Fig. 9. Influence of pore former content on the viscoelastic properties of 59 vol % Al_2O_3 -Sepiolite pastes. The stress sweep results show that increasing the pore former from 20 to 30 vol% significantly weakens the paste's network structure.

Table 6

Summary of measured values of yield stress (τ_y), flow stress (τ_f), and equilibrium storage modulus (G'_{eq}) for 20 and 30 vol% pore former content in 59 vol% Al_2O_3 -Sepiolite pastes, calculated from the data in Fig. 9.

Paste	τ_y (Pa)	τ_f (Pa)	G'_{eq} (Pa)
20 vol%	0.1	0.7	6.4
30 vol%	$7 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$5 \cdot 10^{-2}$	0.3

required extrusion pressure during printing trials.

3.3. Evaluation of printability via DIW

The printability of the optimized paste compositions, which included the graphite-based pore former, was evaluated through the DIW of the scaffold geometries designed from the simulation results (Section 3.1). The assessment focused on two primary criteria directly linked to the rheological properties: extrudability, defined by the ability to produce a continuous and uniform filament at a given pressure, and shape fidelity, which is the capacity of the deposited filament to retain its geometry and support subsequent layers without deformation. The assessment of shape fidelity was performed on the final sintered scaffold structures via optical microscopy.

3.3.1. Al_2O_3 -YSZ paste system

The printing trials for the Al_2O_3 -YSZ system, using formulations containing 20 vol% pore former, immediately confirmed the predictions from the rheological characterization. The paste with 48 vol% solids was found to be unprintable; its excessive stiffness, indicated by the highest measured equilibrium storage modulus (G_{eq}'), required extrusion pressures that exceeded 6 bar, making controlled deposition impossible. In contrast, the 44 vol% and 46 vol% ceramic pastes were successfully extruded. Fig. 10 presents optical microscope images of the final sintered WP90 and WP45 structures. The consolidated scaffolds fabricated using the 44 vol% paste exhibited significant sagging and poor shape fidelity in both the WP90 (Fig. 10a) and WP45 (Fig. 10c) configurations. This deformation, characterized by deformation of filaments and a partial collapse of the porous architecture, is directly attributed to the paste's low stiffness and slow, incomplete structural recovery after deposition, as established in the rheological analysis (Section 3.2.1).

In contrast, the 46 vol% Al_2O_3 -YSZ paste yielded consolidated structures with enhanced stability and high fidelity geometry. As depicted in Fig. 10b (WP90) and Fig. 10d (WP45), the deposited filaments are uniform and well-defined, maintaining the intended open-channel geometry without notable distortions. This superior performance in shape retention correlates directly with the paste's observed rheological profile, which has a sufficiently high storage modulus and rapid structural recovery kinetics necessary to provide structural integrity immediately after deposition.

3.3.2. Al_2O_3 -sepiolite paste system

A similar correlation between rheological properties and printing performance was observed for the Al_2O_3 -Sepiolite system, utilizing formulations that included 20 vol% pore former. The 61 vol% paste was excluded from printing trials, as its extremely stiff nature, predicted by the stress amplitude sweeps, required extrusion pressures greater than 6 bar. The printability of the 57 vol% and 59 vol% pastes is demonstrated in the final sintered structures shown in Fig. 11. The structure printed with the 57 vol% formulation displayed poor shape fidelity, with noticeable sagging of the struts and a loss of the designed porous geometry (Fig. 11a). This result is consistent with its rheological profile, which indicated a weak viscoelastic network and slow, incomplete structural recovery following high shear. In strong contrast, the 59 vol% paste demonstrated excellent printability, producing a scaffold with high geometric precision and stability (Fig. 11b). The filaments retained their shape and supported the subsequent layers effectively, resulting in a well-defined final structure that matches the intended design. This successful fabrication is a consequence of the paste's robust solid-like response at rest and its capacity for rapid and near-complete structural

Fig. 10. Optical microscope images comparing the printability and shape fidelity of Al_2O_3 -YSZ pastes with varying solid loading. Structures fabricated using the 44 vol% paste exhibit significant structural deformation and filament sagging for both (a) WP90 and (c) WP45 configurations. In contrast, the 46 vol% paste demonstrates superior performance, yielding geometrically precise and stable structures for both (b) WP90 and (d) WP45 geometries.

Fig. 11. (a) Optical microscope image of a printed structure using the 57 vol% Al_2O_3 -Sepiolite paste, exhibiting poor shape fidelity and sagging. (b) Image of a structure printed with the 59 vol% paste, demonstrating high geometric precision and stability.

recovery after extrusion. The formulation with 30 vol% pore former, which exhibited reduced stiffness due to the lubricating effect of excess graphite, was also trialed. However, the excessive flow compromised shape fidelity, leading to excessive deformation of the printed structure.

4. Discussion

4.1. Gas flow through the WP90 and WP45 scaffolds

Slight differences in the calculated values between WP90 and WP45 configurations were observed. Reduced values of porosity and permeability for WP45 are associated to the REV values decreasing, compared to WP90. The effect of the 45° turning causes larger volume of interactions between the cylindrical extrude and the initial REV block, impacting on the volume of the allowed space where the gas can interact with the scaffold surface, reducing the surface area for the allowed gas. Moreover, the void space from each 45° turned extrude is an ellipsoid with larger area compared with the circular area from the cylinder.

This effect on the scaffold structure can improve the interaction volume of the gas with the ceramic extrudes. According with the streamline behavior observed in Fig. 3, the developed flow presents a more intricated pathway in the WP45 structure compared with WP90. The observation is supported by the increasing of the pressure drop combined with the outward mass flow rate and unit mass flow decreasing.

The increasing of the interaction volume can produce improved interactions between the gas and the WP arrangement. In the case of WP45 geometry, despite having a slightly smaller geometric area, the intricated pathway is capable to promoting more effective contact of the gas with the available surface, thus improving the utilization of the catalytic surface in the arrangement. Therefore, new catalytic supports improved by the basic WP45 arrangement can be elaborated using the gas flow simulation behavior within the scaffolds as input parameters.

The gas properties play an important role in the developed flow behavior. In this case, CO_2 and H_2 streams were selected due to their wide use in gas phase catalytic reactions and separation applications. The observed decreasing of the parameters presented in Table 2 are corresponding to the values of dynamic viscosity and density between CO_2 and H_2 . Each system will have a set of parameters constricted by the gas properties. However, within the simulation, the pressure surface, velocity streamlines distribution and developed flow behavior was similar between CO_2 and H_2 streams. This observation allows to consider that the presented results of the gas behavior is representative for the gas phase simulation within the ceramic 3D printed scaffolds in WP configurations.

4.2. Rheological characterization

The successful fabrication of geometrically complex ceramic scaffolds via DIW is fundamentally controlled by the rheological properties of the paste. As noted previously, an optimal formulation must satisfy two competing requirements: it must exhibit low viscosity under the high shear conditions within the printing nozzle to ensure smooth, continuous extrusion, and it must rapidly transition to a solid-like state with sufficient stiffness at rest to support its own weight and that of subsequent layers without deformation. This section provides a detailed analysis of the viscoelastic behavior of the Al_2O_3 -YSZ and Al_2O_3 -Sepiolite paste systems, establishing a direct correlation between empirically measured rheological parameters and the observed printability outcomes detailed in Section 3.3. This correlation is essential for developing a predictive framework for paste formulation and quality control.

4.2.1. Rheological behavior: shear-thinning and viscoelasticity

The essential requirement for all DIW pastes formulated in this study is their pronounced shear-thinning (pseudoplastic) behavior. This phenomenon, characterized by a decrease in viscosity with an increasing shear rate, is the primary enabler of the extrusion process. In these concentrated colloidal systems, particles at rest form a flocculated, three-dimensional network structure held together by weak interparticle forces, which imparts the material with its solid-like character (where $G' > G''$). The application of shear stress during extrusion provides the necessary energy to overcome these forces, causing the network to progressively break down. This structural disruption allows particles to disentangle and align in the direction of flow, reducing internal friction and leading to a significant drop in viscosity that facilitates passage through the nozzle.

All paste formulations evaluated in this work displayed a LVR at low strain amplitudes, a domain in which the moduli (G' and G'') remain constant.

4.2.2. Rheological behavior: solid loading and particle morphology

The total volume fraction of the solid phase (solid loading) is a primary control parameter for tuning the rheological profile of high viscosity ceramic pastes. For both the Al_2O_3 -YSZ and Al_2O_3 -Sepiolite systems, a systematic increase in solid loading resulted in an increment of the paste's stiffness and structural integrity, as reflected by increased equilibrium storage modulus (G'_{eq}), yield stress (τ_y) and flow stress (τ_f) values (see Tables 3 and 5). This obvious trend is attributed to the increased particle packing density, which intensifies interparticle interactions and frictional forces, creating a more robust and deformation-resistant network. In the Al_2O_3 -YSZ system, this effect was particularly pronounced. Increasing the solid loading from 44 vol% to 48 vol%

caused the G_{eq}' to increase by two orders of magnitude, from $\approx 1 \cdot 10^3$ Pa to $4 \cdot 10^5$ Pa (Table 3). While a stiffer paste is desirable for shape retention, the 48 vol% formulation proved to be unprintable within our DIW setup. Its extremely high stiffness and yield stress ($\tau_y = 144$ Pa) required feed container air pressures that exceeded the 6 bar limit. Furthermore, its rheological profile from the stress sweep failed to exhibit a crossover point ($G' = G''$), indicating an inability to transition to a predominantly viscous, liquid-like state required for paste flow within DIW process. At the lower end, the 44 vol% paste was easily extrudable but exhibited poor shape fidelity, characterized by significant filament sagging (Fig. 10a and c). This failure is directly linked to its rheological recovery behavior. Its slow and incomplete structural recovery (Fig. 5) highlights a weak network that cannot recover quickly enough and to resist gravitational forces after strut deposition. The 46 vol% paste represented the optimal compromise, having sufficient paste stiffness for structural support (Table 3) and demonstrating a more rapid and complete recovery (Fig. 5) that effectively "locked in" the strut shape immediately after deposition (Fig. 10b and d).

A parallel trend was observed in the Al_2O_3 -Sepiolite system, where the 61 vol% paste was unprintably stiff and the 57 vol% paste was too weak, leading to poor structural recovery (Fig. 8) and sagging (Fig. 11a). The 59 vol% formulation provided the ideal balance of a robust solid-like response at rest combined with rapid and nearly complete structural recovery of the paste, enabling the fabrication of scaffolds through DIW with high geometric precision (Fig. 11b).

The significant finding from this analysis is the substantially higher optimal solid loading achievable in the Al_2O_3 -Sepiolite system (59 vol%) compared to the Al_2O_3 -YSZ system (46 vol%). This distinction is directly attributed to formulation of solid phases within the system. For the Al_2O_3 -YSZ system (volumetric ratio 60:40), the milling of alumina with fine YSZ particles resulted in a high-viscosity starting suspension. In contrast, the viscosity of the starting Al_2O_3 -Sepiolite suspension (volumetric ratio 95:5) was significantly lower (even considering that sepiolite was added after milling step, see Section 2.2). While high-aspect-ratio particles of sepiolite are expected to increase viscosity [24], the low volumetric ratio allowed the sepiolite to act primarily as a rheology modifier without causing prohibitive thickening. The overall rheological response of the Al_2O_3 -Sepiolite pastes confirm this rheology modifier role; the systems exhibited a well-defined solid-like response at rest ($G' > G''$), which is attributed to a "log-jam" effect that creates an exceptionally efficient and rigid framework at rest. This rigidity is a highly beneficial feature for shape retention in DIW, and its efficient formation permits a much higher volume of solid phases to be loaded before the paste becomes unprintable. This result demonstrates a powerful principle for DIW paste formulation, where particle morphology can be used to maximize solid loading while controlling the printability window.

4.2.3. Rheological behavior: influence of pore former on paste viscoelasticity

The addition of a sacrificial, carbon-based pore former introduced another layer of complexity, with the graphite particles causing fundamentally different rheological responses in the two paste systems. This highlights the previous observation in Al_2O_3 -Sepiolite system, that the effect of a solid phases within colloidal system is not intrinsic, but is instead dictated by its interactions with the rest of the particles within the network. Within the 46 vol% Al_2O_3 -YSZ paste, increasing the graphite content from 15 to 20 vol% caused the reinforcement of the solid network, making the paste stiffer and more elastic (Fig. 6). This was quantitatively confirmed by an increase in G_{eq}' from $1 \cdot 10^4$ Pa to $2 \cdot 10^4$ Pa, along with resulting increases in τ_y and τ_f (Table 4). In this system, the graphite particles, which have a particle size comparable to the alumina but with more plate-like morphology, appear to function as an additional solid phase. They likely fill interstitial voids in the alumina-YSZ packing, increasing the effective solid volume fraction and the density of particle-particle contact points. This leads to greater

interparticle friction and a stronger resistance to deformation, hence the observed increase in the viscoelastic moduli.

In strong contrast, an opposite effect was observed in the 59 vol% Al_2O_3 -Sepiolite system. Increasing the graphite content from 20 to 30 vol% induced a dramatic weakening of the viscoelastic network, causing a significant reduction in both G' and G'' (Fig. 9). The strength of the sepiolite-based network is derived from the mechanical entanglement and frictional contacts between the sepiolite fibers. It is hypothesized that the graphite particles in this case function as a lubricant within this paste system, reducing the entanglement effect of sepiolite phase. These graphite particles may situate themselves between the sepiolite fibers, creating slip planes that reduce the coefficient of friction and allow the fibers to slide past one another more easily under an applied stress. This disruption of the mechanical interlocking mechanism effectively plasticizes the paste, reducing its overall stiffness and enhancing its flowability, as reflected in the lower values in Table 6. While this effect lowered the required extrusion pressure, the excessive flow compromised shape fidelity, leading to deformation of the printed structure. This comparative analysis reveals a critical design consideration: the rheological impact of additives such as pore formers is highly dependent on the morphology of the primary network-forming particles.

4.3. DIW printability criteria

Printability in DIW is governed by two main concepts: the controlled extrusion of the paste and the ability of the deposited filament to maintain its shape after deposition. Both aspects are directly linked to the rheological properties investigated in this study. The correlation between the rheological data (Section 3.2) and the printing outcomes (Section 3.3) allows for the establishment of a quantitative "printability window" for the developed paste systems.

4.3.1. Extrudability

The primary requirement for extrudability is the shear-thinning behavior of the paste [25–27], which ensures lower extrusion pressure at a given printing speed compared to Newtonian or shear-thickening materials. This behavior was evident in all formulations evaluated. However, a more critical parameter for initiating and sustaining flow is the flow stress (τ_f). The printable 44 and 46 vol% Al_2O_3 -YSZ pastes possessed τ_f values of 22.3 Pa and 423 Pa, respectively (Table 3). These values are consistent with reported data for binder-containing ceramic pastes, where yield τ_f typically ranges from 25 Pa to 5.0×10^3 Pa, with optimal values generally falling within a narrower range of 100 to 2.0×10^3 Pa [9,14]. Binder-free ceramic pastes, in contrast, generally exhibit much higher yield stresses, with $G' \approx G''$ values exceeding 10^3 Pa [28].

In contrast, the printable 57 and 59 vol% Al_2O_3 -Sepiolite pastes possessed significantly lower τ_f values of 0.02 Pa and 0.7 Pa, respectively (Table 5). Although these values fall well below established benchmarks, the printability of these high-solid-loading formulations was very good. Observed printability and high shape fidelity is attributed to exceptionally rapid structural recovery kinetics (Fig. 8) of these Al_2O_3 -Sepiolite pastes. That is, it clearly indicates that the recovery kinetics is a predominant factor for DIW printability and not the absolute flow stress value.

The 48 vol% Al_2O_3 -YSZ and 61 vol% Al_2O_3 -Sepiolite pastes were deemed unprintable, as their extremely high stiffness required extrusion pressures exceeding the 6-bar limit of the equipment. This highlights that while shear-thinning is necessary, DIW printability is ultimately dictated by a balance of factors rather than a single parameter. The criteria established in this study are therefore specific to the pastes and printing conditions used, as no standardized methodology for these procedures currently exists.

4.3.2. Shape fidelity

The second set of parameters relates to the shape fidelity of the paste

after deposition. It is crucial that extruded strut retains its geometry without sagging to ensure the shape fidelity, especially critical during the stacking of successive layers with pronounced bridging geometries. This capacity is dependent on a combination of the paste's stiffness at rest (G_{eq}'), its resistance to initial deformation (τ_y), and its ability to rapidly reform its internal network after extrusion (structural recovery).

The equilibrium storage modulus (G_{eq}') reflects the stiffness of the paste at rest and proved to be a primary indicator of DIW performance. For printable ceramic pastes, reported G_{eq}' values range widely, with many falling between 25 and 200 kPa [9,25,29,30]. The optimal pastes in this study, 46 vol% Al_2O_3 -YSZ and 59 vol% Al_2O_3 -Sepiolite, demonstrated superior shape fidelity, correlating with their robust G_{eq}' values (Tables 3 and 5). In contrast, formulations with insufficient stiffness, such as the 44 vol% Al_2O_3 -YSZ paste ($G_{eq}' \approx 10^3$ Pa) and 57 vol% Al_2O_3 -Sepiolite paste ($G_{eq}' \approx 0.3$ Pa), consistently failed due to sagging (Fig. 10a, c, 11a).

An optimal yield stress (τ_y) is also critical for balancing extrudability and structural fidelity. It must be high enough to resist deformation but low enough to allow paste flow to initiate at reasonable pressures (>5 bar). For example, the 44 vol% Al_2O_3 -YSZ paste exhibited a τ_y value below the commonly accepted minimum threshold of 10 Pa, rendering it unsuitable for printing due to inadequate shape retention, as confirmed in the printing trials (Fig. 10a and c). Whereas, the 46 vol% Al_2O_3 -YSZ formulation demonstrated a moderate τ_y values that enabled successful layer stacking and structural integrity. These observed τ_y values are within the literature benchmarks for alumina-based printable supports, despite not fully conforming to the optimal range. This observation correlates with studies utilizing similar rheological profiles in alumina systems, where moderate τ_y values enabled successful layer stacking and structural integrity [25,27,29].

A similar correlation between rheological parameters and shape fidelity was observed in the Al_2O_3 -Sepiolite system. The 57 vol% formulation, as noted previously, produced scaffolds with poor shape fidelity and significant sagging (Fig. 11a). This outcome is directly attributed to its rheological properties, which featured a weak viscoelastic network with a low equilibrium storage modulus (G_{eq}') and yield stress (τ_y) (Table 5), combined with slow and incomplete structural recovery (Fig. 8). In contrast, the superior geometric precision of the scaffolds printed with the 59 vol% paste (Fig. 11b) is in coincidence with its optimum rheological properties for DIW process. This formulation exhibited a robust solid-like response, characterized by higher G_{eq}' and τ_y values, and critically, a rapid and near-complete structural recovery (Fig. 8), which was essential for maintaining post-extrusion strut's shape.

Finally, the speed and scale of structural recovery after extrusion are of high importance for fixing the strut's shape. The 46 vol% Al_2O_3 -YSZ paste exhibited a higher recovery (63%) compared to the 44 vol% paste (53%) after approximately 120 s (Fig. 5). Although neither paste achieved 100% recovery at a given evaluation time, these results are favorable for DIW and align with values reported in the literature [31]. This faster recovery directly correlated with the superior print quality of the 46 vol% paste. Similarly, the rapid and nearly complete recovery of the 59 vol% Al_2O_3 -Sepiolite paste (Fig. 8) was a key factor in its excellent printability and shape retention in this case (Fig. 11b).

5. Conclusions

This work successfully implemented a sequential workflow where predictive CFD simulations identified the 45° WP orientation as the optimal architecture for gas flow. This finding directly informed the experimental stage, where the rheological properties of Al_2O_3 -organic paste was tailored to ensure the structural integrity of the complex WP45 design during 3D printing. The high dimensional fidelity of the printed scaffolds validates this approach as a viable strategy for DIW ceramic scaffolds elaboration.

The CFD analysis demonstrated that simple modifications to the strut

alignment in consecutive layers can be used to tune scaffold properties for specific process requirements. The WP90 configuration was shown to favor high mass flow, evidenced by a lower pressure drop, whereas the WP45 configuration created a more intricate fluid pathway, maximizing gas-scaffold interactions at the cost of higher flow resistance. This finding establishes a clear design principle for tailoring scaffold geometry to either mass-transfer or reaction-limited processes.

The successful DIW of these structures was contingent upon the parallel development of high-performance ceramic pastes. A notable finding was that the incorporation of a minor fraction (5 vol%) of fibrous sepiolite enabled the formulation of pastes with solid loadings (59 vol%) compared to systems based on conventional technical Al_2O_3 -YSZ ceramic particles. This was attributed to efficient, mechanically interlocked network formed by Al_2O_3 particles and acid treated sepiolite fibers. Furthermore, this work studied the system-dependent role of secondary solid phases; graphite pore former acted as a structure reinforcing agent in the Al_2O_3 -YSZ system but functioned as a lubricant in the fibrous Al_2O_3 -Sepiolite network, demonstrating that the rheological impact of additives is critically dictated by the chemistry and morphology of the particles.

By correlating the measured rheological properties with the final printing outcomes, this study established a quantitative DIW printability window for given composition pastes. Successful fabrication of structures with high shape fidelity was achieved with pastes exhibiting a specific combination of properties: a robust equilibrium storage modulus (G_{eq}') in the range of 10^4 Pa, a yield stress (τ_y) sufficient to resist gravitational deformation, and rapid, near-complete structural recovery after extrusion. Formulations that did not meet these criteria consistently resulted in printed structures with significant geometry defects, such as strut sagging or even a complete collapse.

In summary, the presented framework provides a systematic approach for the rational design of DIW-fabricated components. This study demonstrates a systematic framework for the design and fabrication of Al_2O_3 scaffolds. By using CFD to pre-select optimal 3D architectures and experimental rheology to ensure their printable fidelity, the gap between theoretical gas-flow optimization and physical manufacturing is addressed. This methodology is particularly relevant for the development of advanced ceramic components in catalysis.

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Declaration of use of AI-assisted technologies in the manuscript preparation process

The authors utilized the AI tool Grammarly to enhance the grammar and style of this manuscript. Following its use, the authors reviewed, edited, and approved the final content and take full responsibility for the published article.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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